

Pre-Reading Activities and Reading Comprehension in an English as a Second Language Classroom

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ABSTRACT: Reading comprehension is the skill of understanding and interpret the meaning of a text. Engaging and exposing students to more reading related activities with interaction and critical thinking would be of great help to enhance the comprehension skills of the students. The purpose of this study is to find out the effectiveness of pre-reading activities such as KWL strategy, graphics information, WH-Questions and vocabulary in improving the learners' reading comprehension skill. The respondents were the limited sixty (60) grade 9 students of Sta Catalina National High School for the school year 2022-2023. Two groups of respondents comprised thirty (30) students who undergone the treatment and served as the first experimental group while the other thirty (30) students served as the second experimental group who used two different pre-reading activities. The first experimental group undergone the pre-reading activities, KWL strategy and Graphics Information while the other one undergone WH-Questions and Vocabulary. Based on the results of the experiment, there is no significant difference in the mean pretest and posttest of the experimental group 1 using the KWL and graphics information pre-reading activities. However, there is significant difference in the direct recalling questions reading competence. In terms of mean pretest and posttest of the experimental group 2 using WH-questions and vocabulary, there is also no significant difference. Same with experimental group 1, only in direct recalling questions found significant. It is also found out that there is no significant difference between the pretest scores of the two experimental groups of respondents before using the pre-reading activities. In terms of posttest of the two experimental groups, all the four variables have no significant difference although some improvement in the posttest scores is evident, only direct recalling questions were found to have significant difference in the mean posttest scores. The result of the scores of the experimental group 1 is higher than that of experimental group 2.

KEYWORDS: graphics information, KWL strategy, reading comprehension, vocabulary, WH-questions

INTRODUCTION

Comprehension is the most important part of reading because it involves the ability to grasp the meaning of a written passage effectively. Nowadays, students need to be able to adjust their reading strategies, manage their learning, and monitor their progress in order to become skilled readers who can extract information from the text, think logically, and reflect critically while reading. To achieve this, students must be given a wide range of reading and writing tasks that include effective approaches or methods for improving reading comprehension. quality, use the details in the reference and properly cite them [1].

Using various methods and techniques plays a crucial role in enhancing students' reading comprehension skills and promoting higher-level learning. English teachers have a responsibility to employ diverse reading strategies and encourage critical thinking to help students understand complex texts. Reading comprehension involves multiple factors such as cognition, language, and socio-cultural aspects, which can make it difficult for teachers to develop an efficient and effective reading strategy [2].

Since reading strategies and/or tactics truly help the learners in understanding what they read, its effectiveness is widely accepted. Language teachers must recognize the significance of reading engagement, though. Reading engagement is important for children whose reading comprehension is somewhat difficult for them because of the instant magic and delight that comes from reading for pleasure as well as the long-term learning and life benefits this can provide. According to Reading engagement is a result of a combination of reading strategies that comprise mental states or dispositions known as "Habits of Mind" (HoM). Managing impulsivity, empathic listening, reasonable and adaptable thinking, and persistence are some of the traits that make up the Habits of Mind. These elements are important to help students develop effective problem- solving skills by enhancing their skills to ask the proper questions, reflect on the information at hand, and think critically Reading objectives in language courses are revitalized to build HoM abilities in reading practices as a result of reading comprehension linked with "Habits of Mind" (HoM) promotion of interaction between students and reading content. Additionally, language teachers stress collaborative reading activities to give their

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students a social setting that might enhance reading comprehension. This consists of group discussions, home reading assignments, and other reading-related activities that encourage critical reflection when reading and engaging with texts as well as interpretive discussion among the students. [3].

Thus, involving and exposing students to more interactive, critical-thinking reading-related activities would be beneficial in improving the students' comprehension skills in an English classroom.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The study aimed to find out the effect of pre-reading activities in the reading comprehension skills of the students. It focused on two sections in grade 9 who served as experimental group 1 and 2.

This study tested the significant difference between the mean pretest and posttest scores of the Experimental Group 1 of respondents before and after using the pre-reading activities such as KWL and graphics information. In the same manner, experimental group 2 was tested its significant difference before and after using the pre-reading activities such as WH question and vocabulary.

It was also tested the significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores of the two experimental groups of respondents before and after using the pre-reading activities.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This research employed the quasi-experimental design in determining the effect of pre-reading activities on the reading comprehension skills of the respondents. The researcher has used two experimental groups of respondents using the pretest-posttest design. Quasi-experimental design is a useful tool when it comes to situations where true experiments cannot be used for ethical or practical reasons. Quasi-experimental design tries to find a group that is similar to the group receiving the treatment in terms of their initial characteristics. This similar group is called the comparison group. By comparing the outcomes of the treatment group with the outcomes of the comparison group, we can understand what would have happened if the program or policy hadn't been implemented. This helps us determine whether the program or policy had a direct impact on the outcomes we observe [4].

Respondents of the Study

This study used sixty (60) grade 9 students from Sta. Catalina National High School who served as respondents of the study. The first group of thirty students belonged to the first experimental group while the remaining thirty students served as the second experimental group. The first experimental group have undergone the KWL and infographics strategy while the second group used the WH and Vocabulary strategy of teaching and developing comprehension skill. In experimental group 1, 40% were males and 60% were females while in experimental group 2, 30% were males and 70% were females. Cluster sampling technique was used in this study. Two sections of Grade 9 English students of the researcher were considered as the respondents.

Research Instrument

To get the impact of pre-reading activities using the four strategies such as KWL, infographics, Wh - questions, and vocabulary to the reading competence of the two groups of respondents, which were comprised of thirty (30) respondents for experimental group 1 and another thirty (30) for experimental group 2. Before the implementation of the study, lesson exemplars for the whole duration of the experiment and a Table of Specifications were prepared by the researcher which were aligned to DepEd MELCs. Pretest and posttest, adapted modified tests were also prepared for the experiment. These instruments were first validated by the subject specialist. For content and face validity, the said instruments were checked and validated by the three external validators. The adapted modified tests were used, consisting of 50 items that measured the reading competence of the respondents, such as identifying main idea and key details; sequencing, direct recalling questions, making inferences or predictions and identifying unfamiliar vocabulary.

Both groups have undergone the treatment and were given posttest and compared to that of pretest. The same set of questions was administered for the two groups.

For the lessons to be discussed, the researcher prepared two sets of lesson exemplars: one set for experimental group 1, which applied the pre-reading activities, KWL strategy and graphics information (infographics), and another set for experimental group 2, which applied the vocabulary and wh-questions. These pre-reading activities were usually applied either in the Introduction Phase and Development Phase, wherein the students would be focusing on understanding what they reading, which helped them to understand the lesson better.

Before the conduct of the experiment, with the help of her statistician, the instruments were tested for reliability and validity and undergone pilot testing. After the given tests, it was submitted to the statistician for analysis.

Research Procedure

The researcher conducted the study during the Third Quarter of the S.Y 2022-2023. Lessons were based on the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) provided by the Department of Education (DepEd) and prepared IDEA Lesson Exemplar. Lessons were discussed using pre-reading activities during the duration of the class to keep the students engaged. The four pre-reading

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activities, such as KWL, Graphics Information (infographic), WH-Questions and Vocabulary were used and divided into lessons during the duration of the experiment.

The researcher prepared the instrument to be used in the pretest-posttest evaluation which is an adapted modified test to measure students' reading competence. The instrument was validated first by the subject specialist. IDEA Lesson Exemplars (LE) and Tables of Specifications (TOS) were validated too.

For content and face validity, the said instruments were checked and validated by the three external validators. Then, the researcher incorporated the suggestions provided by the external validators. Afterwards, with the approval of the researcher's adviser and statistician, pilot testing was conducted to ensure the test's reliability. There were twelve (12) grade 10 students who participated in the pilot testing. Then, the researcher tallied the responses and subjected them to item analysis.

The result of the item analysis was used to revise or alter some of the questions in the instrument. After the instrument was finalized, the researcher administered the pretest to the respondents as the first assessment of their reading comprehension. The grade 9 respondents answered the pretest in one hour.

To ensure the participation of the respondents, the researcher herself personally taught the students for the whole duration of the experiment.

During the experiment, the lessons intended for that week were discussed by the researcher using pre-reading activities with the group of students. Two groups of respondents, namely experimental group 1 and experimental group 2 were used but during the first day of the implementation, both groups of respondents were asked to take the pretest first.

For experimental group 1, the researcher applied pre-reading activities such as KWL and Graphics Information (infographic). These activities were applied before discussing the main topics, which could be found either in the introduction phase or development phase of the lesson. The researcher discussed how these pre-reading activities may help them understand a text. Respondents were asked to read the texts then apply these pre-reading activities and answer on one whole sheet of paper. Afterwards, during the discussion and checking of the activities, there was a sharing of answers and ideas which led to the main lesson.

In the same manner, experimental group 2 was also taught using other pre-reading activities such as WH-questions and vocabulary. These pre-reading activities were also used either in the introduction or development phase. The researcher discussed the pre-reading activities and their uses. Same with experimental group 1, respondents were also asked to read the given texts then apply these pre-reading activities and answer on one whole sheet of paper. Afterwards, during the discussion and checking of the activities, same as experimental group 1, there was a sharing of answers and ideas which led to the main lesson.

Right after the experiment, both groups were given a posttest. This is to find out if the reading competence has improved after using the pre-reading activities. The researcher then collected the data and submitted it to the statistician for the treatment. It was tabulated, analyzed, and interpreted.

For ethical consideration, the researcher sought permission from the Division Schools Superintendent, District Supervisor, and from the Principal of Sta. Catalina National High School for the conduct of the study.

Statistical Treatment of Data

After the gathering of the data, this was subjected for statistical treatment. The researcher tabulated, analyzed, and interpreted the results. For better analysis and discussions, the following statistical tools were used.

Mean and Standard deviation were utilized. To get the significant difference of the pretest and posttest of the two experimental groups of respondents, Test of difference was used. T- test for dependent and independent means were used for inferential analyses [5].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Part 1. Mean Pretest and Posttest Scores of the Two Groups of Respondents

Table 1

Mean Pre-test Scores of Experimental Group 1 in Reading Comprehension before using the Pre-reading Activities such as KWL and Graphics information

Reading Comprehension	Mean	SD	Verbal
			Interpretation
Identifying main idea and key details	5.27	1.62	Satisfactory
Sequencing	7.87	1.76	Very Satisfactory
Direct recalling questions	6.60	2.58	Very Satisfactory
Making inferences or predictions	5.07	2.21	Satisfactory
Identifying Unfamiliar vocabulary	3.53	1.48	Fair
Total	5.67	1.97	

Legend: 8.00-10.00 – Excellent, 6.00-7.99 – Very Satisfactory, 4.00-5.99 – Satisfactory, 2.00-3.99 – Fair, 0.00-1.99 – Unsatisfactory

The table presents the pretest scores of experimental group 1 in reading comprehension before using KWL and Graphics Information. It can be seen from the results that in terms of identifying main idea, the respondents got only satisfactory rating with a mean of 5.27 which indicate that they can identify simple ideas when reading. In terms of sequencing, and direct recalling questions, the students got a very satisfactory rating of 7.87 and 6.60 which indicate that the students have the ability to recognize to sequence events accordingly. In terms of sequencing and direct recalling questions 10 was the highest score obtained by some of the respondents. This proved that students can quite understand the story. Sequencing of events is a valuable strategy for comprehension for several reasons. It aids students of varying abilities in effectively organizing information and ideas. This skill is not only significant for problem-solving across various subjects such as science and social studies but also enhances overall comprehension [5]. By encouraging students to identify different elements of a story, they become better equipped to recount or summarize the story to others. Instead of retelling the entire story as a whole, students learn to break it down into distinct parts like the beginning, middle, and end. Engaging in sequencing activities allows students to analyze the structure of the text and the story, ultimately bolstering their writing skills. It is important for teachers to ask well-designed questions to help students improve their understanding. Good questions can lead to new ideas, encourage discussion, and help students explore a topic thoroughly. On the other hand, poorly constructed questions can hinder learning by causing confusion, making students feel intimidated, and restricting their creative thinking. Therefore, teachers should focus on asking clear and straightforward questions instead of using the old method of simply asking students to recall information. As to making inferences and predictions, the students got satisfactory rating of 5.07 indicating that they can draw conclusions with minimal errors, while identifying unfamiliar vocabulary got a fair rating, the lowest result which indicates that the students have the ability to identify unfamiliar words in the passage but with a little difficulty [6]. Vocabulary knowledge as a crucial factor influencing reading comprehension in both first and second language acquisition. Insufficient vocabulary size and inadequate understanding of word meanings frequently pose obstacles for learners in comprehending the intended message conveyed in a text. None of the students got an excellent rating.

Table 2
Mean Pretest Scores of the Experimental Group 2 in Reading Comprehension before using the Pre-reading Activities such as WH Question and Vocabulary

pretest experimental group 2	Mean	SD	Verbal
			Interpretation
Identifying main idea and key details	5.72	1.53	Satisfactory
Sequencing	7.66	2.27	Very Satisfactory
Direct recalling questions	7.17	2.21	Very Satisfactory
Making inferences or predictions	5.03	2.15	Satisfactory
Identifying unfamiliar vocabulary	3.59	1.94	Fair
Total	5.83	1.87	

Legend: 8.00-10.00 – Excellent, 6.00-7.99 – Very Satisfactory, 4.00-5.99 – Satisfactory, 2.00-3.99 – Fair, 0.00-1.99 – Unsatisfactory

Table 2 presents the mean scores of the experimental group 2 respondents in reading comprehension before using the WH questions and Vocabulary activities. It can be seen from the data that before the conduct of the study, the students are already doing well in sequencing and direct recall question similar to experimental group 1 with 7.66 and 7.17 means respectively. This indicates that they can answer the questions directly after reading the passage. It was obvious that both groups were good in terms of sequencing and direct recalling questions. Sequencing affects children's reading comprehension. Children who were better at understanding what they read tended to create more accurate sequences compared to those who struggled with comprehension. This suggests that being able to put things in the right order is helpful for understanding. In terms of making predictions, the students can draw conclusions with minimal errors with 5.03 mean scores or rating [7]. In terms of unfamiliar vocabulary, students got only a fair performance or mean scores of 3.59. This suggests that students can find meaning through context clues but with a little difficulty. Understanding words is crucial for understanding what you read. If you don't know the meaning of most words, it's hard to understand the text. It's important to know the meaning of unfamiliar words so you can understand what a sentence is saying. If you don't understand a difficult word, it can make it difficult to understand the whole text. Having a dictionary can help you find the meaning of difficult words [8]. This also means that students may find it harder to understand everything due to usual routine done in an English class.

Table 3
Mean Posttest Scores of Experimental Group 1 in Reading Comprehension after using the Pre-reading Activities such as KWL and Graphics Information

posttest experimental group 1	Mean	SD	Verbal
			Interpretation
Identifying main idea and key details	5.90	1.77	Satisfactory
Sequencing	8.13	2.40	Excellent
Direct recalling questions	9.23	0.90	Excellent
Making inferences or predictions	5.43	1.87	Satisfactory
Identifying unfamiliar vocabulary	4.03	1.43	Satisfactory
Total	6.54	1.75	

Legend: 8.00-10.00 – Excellent, 6.00-7.99 – Very Satisfactory, 4.00-5.99 – Satisfactory, 2.00-3.99 – Fair, 0.00-1.99 – Unsatisfactory

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Table 3 presents the results of the posttest mean scores of the experimental group 1 in reading comprehension after using the KWL and Graphics Information during their reading classes. Based on the results, the students got a mean of 5.90 with satisfactory rating. This means that there is a small percent of improvement in identifying main idea and key details based on the mean score results. However, in terms of sequencing and direct recall questions, means of 8.13 and 9.23 indicate an increase in the mean scores and show improvement after using the KWL and Graphics Information during reading classes. It is also evident that among the 5 reading comprehension skills, students still good when it comes to sequencing and direct recalling questions since they can read the details in the texts. In terms of identifying unfamiliar vocabulary, it went from being fair to improving to satisfactory. This implies that exposing students to reading activities would help enhance their reading comprehension skills because being engaged in a learning environment increases attention of the students and focus on what is discussed to them, thus, higher performance is expected [9].

Table 4

Mean Posttest Scores of the Experimental Group 2 in Reading Comprehension after using the Pre-reading Activities such as WH Question and Vocabulary

posttest experimental group 2	Mean	SD	Verbal
			Interpretation
Identifying main idea and key details	5.59	1.18	Satisfactory
Sequencing	8.41	1.78	Excellent
Direct recalling questions	8.45	1.84	Excellent
Making inferences or predictions	4.90	2.01	Satisfactory
Identifying unfamiliar vocabulary	4.48	2.82	Satisfactory
Total	6.37	1.84	

Legend: 8.00-10.00 – Excellent, 6.00-7.99 – Very Satisfactory, 4.00-5.99 – Satisfactory, 2.00-3.99 – Fair, 0.00-1.99 – Unsatisfactory

Results show significant improvement similar to that of experimental group 1 who used different types of activities in reading. This can be seen from the increase in the mean scores of sequencing and direct recall questions with 8.41 and 8.45 means show excellent performance in the two skills after using the WH and Vocabulary activities. This means that students find it easy to understand what they read because in direct recalling questions answers can be found in the passage already while sequencing needs a thorough reading so they can arrange the story or events accordingly. In the same manner, making inferences or predictions and identifying unfamiliar vocabulary also show an increase in the posttest scores from fair performance to satisfactory performance with means of 4.90 and 4.48 respectively. This implies that despite a small increase in the mean scores it also suggests that using the pre-reading activities somehow helped them to understand better what they read. However, in terms of identifying main ideas and key details, no increase in the mean scores and retain in the satisfactory performance. This implies that they still have the skills in identifying main idea and key details in the passages or story they read but not given much focus since intensive reading is necessary for the students before identifying the main idea and key details. Still, they belong to satisfactory performance and none of them got an unsatisfactory rating. Same in experimental group 1, it is also evident that among the 5 reading comprehension skills, students are still good when it comes to sequencing and direct recalling questions since they can read the details in the texts. Researcher believed that making inferences or predictions is not easy for students because you have to read between the lines. It needs deeper reading and make their own discoveries about the text [10], that is probably the reason they remain satisfactory.

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Part II. Test of Significant Difference between the Pretest and Posttest Scores of the Two Experimental Groups

Table 5

Mean Difference between the Pretest and Posttest Scores of the Experimental Group 1 before and after using the KWL and Graphics Information

Reading Comprehension	Pretest		Posttest		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Verbal Interpretation
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD				
Identifying main idea and key details	5.27	1.62	5.90	1.77	-1.698	29	0.100	Not Significant
Sequencing	7.87	1.76	8.13	2.40	-0.554	29	0.584	Not Significant
Direct recalling questions	6.60	2.58	9.23	0.90	-5.479	29	0.000	Significant
Making inferences or predictions	5.07	2.21	5.43	1.87	-0.905	29	0.373	Not Significant
Identifying unfamiliar vocabulary	3.53	1.48	4.03	1.43	-1.634	29	0.113	Not Significant
Total	5.67	3.09	6.54	5.04				

Legend: Sig (2-tailed) \leq .05 (Significant); Sig (2-tailed) \geq .05 (Not significant)

Table 5 shows the results of the test of difference between the pretest and posttest of the experimental group 1 after using the KWL and Graphics Information activities. Based on the pretest and posttest results, no significant difference when tested at 0.05 level of significance. This is very evident with the t-values of -1.698 for identifying main idea, -0.554 for sequencing, -0.905 for making inferences and predictions and 1.634 for unfamiliar vocabulary respectively. With P-values of 0.100, 0.584, 0.373, and 0.113 at .05 level of significance implies that no significant difference using the KWL and graphics information with the pretest and posttest scores since they almost fall under the same performance rating but significant improvement or increase in the scores is very apparent. In terms of direct recalling questions found to have significant difference with a t-value of -5.479 with p-value of 0.000 at .05 level of significance. Direct recalling questions in reading comprehension aim to help children understand what they read by using what they already know. This prior knowledge can come from their own experiences or what they know about words, places, animals, or events. Questioning is a strategy taught to students to help them interact with the text and improve their understanding. By asking good questions, students can check if they're understanding the text and make it clearer for themselves. Results indicate that the use of pre-reading activities encourages higher levels of student's performance and motivates them to practice higher level of critical thinking skills in the comprehension level of the students. Moreover, reading engagement matters because it can help develop higher level of focus and concentration and improves reading comprehension skills of the students which is of great importance in the acquisition of English as a second language. Thus, exposure to pre-reading activities matters to the student's success in reading.

Table 6

Difference between the Mean Pretest and Posttest Scores of the Experimental Group 2 before and after using the WH Question and Vocabulary

Reading Comprehension	Pretest		Posttest		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Verbal Interpretation
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD				
Identifying main idea and key details	5.72	1.53	5.59	1.18	0.386	28	0.702	Not Significant
Sequencing	7.66	2.27	8.41	1.78	-1.702	28	0.100	Not Significant
Direct recalling questions	7.17	2.21	8.45	1.84	-2.774	28	0.010	Significant
Making inferences or predictions	5.03	2.15	4.90	2.01	0.351	28	0.728	Not Significant
Identifying unfamiliar vocabulary	3.59	1.94	4.48	2.82	-1.803	28	0.082	Not Significant
Total	5.83	2.13	6.37	2.05				

Legend: Sig (2-tailed) \leq .05 (Significant); Sig (2-tailed) \geq .05 (Not significant)

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The figures on the table present the results of the statistical analysis of the pretest and posttest of the experimental group 2 after using the WH- questions and Vocabulary. Based on the results, all reading comprehension skills such identifying main idea, sequencing, making inferences or predictions and identifying unfamiliar vocabulary were found to have no significant difference at all. These are based on the t-values of 0.386, -1.702, 0.351 and -1.803 and p-values of 0.702, 0.100, 0.728, and 0.082 treated at .05 level of significance. These results suggest that during the conduct of the pretest and posttest, the respondents already had background knowledge of the reading comprehension skills, however, it can be seen from the means that despite no significant difference, an increase in the mean scores is very apparent. Though, in making inferences, posttest decreases a little since it involves deeper understanding of the passage and involves use of evidence and reasoning. Among the five reading comprehension skills, only direct recall questions were found to have significant difference in the pretest and posttest scores of the respondents. A t- value of -2.774 and p-value of 0.010 at .05 level of significance indicates that an impressive increase in their mean scores is evident. This implies that direct recall activity is a questioning strategy that enables the reader to decode the text, understand and remember the information. It will be easier for them since all answers can be found from the material they read. Well-constructed questions help students understand better. It makes them think deeply, talk about their ideas, and explore the topic thoroughly. It's also a helpful way for students to check if they really understand what they're reading.

Part III. Test of Difference between the Pretest Scores of the Two Experimental Groups of Respondents before and after using the Pre-reading Activities

Table 7
Test of Difference between the Pretest Scores of the Two Experimental Groups of Respondents before using the Pre-reading Activities

Reading Comprehension	Experimental Group 1		Experimental Group 2		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Verbal Interpretation
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD				
Identifying main idea and key details	5.27	1.62	5.73	1.51	-1.156	58	0.252	Not Significant
Sequencing	7.87	1.76	7.67	2.23	0.386	58	0.701	Not Significant
Direct recalling questions	6.60	2.58	7.13	2.18	-0.865	58	0.391	Not Significant
Making inferences or predictions	5.07	2.21	5.03	2.11	0.060	58	0.953	Not Significant
Identifying unfamiliar vocabulary	3.53	1.48	3.53	1.93	0.000	58	1.000	Not Significant
Total	5.67	2.17	5.82	2.06				

Legend: Sig (2-tailed) \leq .05 (Significant); Sig (2-tailed) \geq .05 (Not significant)

Results show that when tested and compared the two pretest results of the two experimental groups no significant difference was found. This can be seen from the p-values of 0.252 for identifying main idea and key details, 0.701 for sequencing, 0.391 for direct recalling questions, 0.953 for making inferences or predictions and 1.000 for identifying unfamiliar vocabulary. This implies that the students have almost the same level of understanding and skills in reading comprehension. They have both satisfactory and fair performances during the first phase of the study where pre-reading activities were not yet given by the teacher. But in terms of identifying the main idea and key details, experimental group 2 got a higher mean score than experimental group 1. In sequencing experimental group 1 got a higher mean score than experimental group 2. In direct recalling questions, experimental group 2 got a higher mean score than experimental group 1. In terms of making inferences or predictions, experimental group 1 got a higher mean score than experimental in a matter of .04 points while in identifying unfamiliar vocabulary, both groups got the same mean scores. Finding the main idea of a text is the first thing you need to do to learn how to summarize important information. It's an important skill for understanding what you read, but it can be hard to teach and for students to grasp. Once you get good at figuring out the main idea and the details, it becomes easier to read more advanced texts and figure out the main idea. This skill is important to practice from a young age because it helps with analyzing texts more deeply. Mastering the main idea and key details will serve as a foundation as students are assigned more advanced reading and must draw out the main idea. This then builds to complex analysis, making it crucial that students start practicing this skill at a young age [11]. In terms of sequencing, significance of teaching sequencing to young children was emphasized. Sequencing is an important skill for kids to learn because it helps with reading, understanding, and writing. Sequencing means putting things in order, like knowing what comes first, second, and last. We use sequencing every day to organize our tasks and understand events in our lives. However, some children may find sequencing challenging, especially when telling a story. Developing sequencing skills in students is crucial as it helps them better understand

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and comprehend what they read [12]. In direct recalling questions, it was stated that the method of asking direct or recall questions can be used for both fiction and informational texts. When reading fiction, skilled readers are able to identify and explain the important events, conflicts, and decisions. They also use this skill to understand literary elements. When reading informational texts, good readers are able to distinguish between information that is important and information that is not necessary [13]. This is one of the reasons why the students got higher and significant results in terms of direct recalling questions. In the reading class, it's crucial to learn how to make inferences to understand the text better. Inferences help readers go beyond what's written and find deeper meanings or make their own discoveries. When teachers teach comprehension strategies like making inferences, it improves students' overall understanding of what they read. Understanding words is crucial for understanding what you read. If you don't know the meaning of most words, it's hard to understand the text. When children read advanced books, they come across new words that they don't know from talking. It's important to know the meaning of unfamiliar words so you can understand what a sentence is saying. If you don't understand a difficult word, it can make it difficult to understand the whole text. Having a dictionary can help you find the meaning of difficult. .Based on the results, among the five reading competencies, only the direct recalling questions were significant. Students found it quite easy because, upon reading the text, they found the answers within the text. Even if there's a little improvement in the results, for the teacher, it is still an achievement. Thus, results also show that there's a need to improve more their reading comprehension skills through reading activities since it increases the understanding of the text and encourages more to learn about the subject matter cover in the text [14]. Moreover, giving students pre-reading activities during reading class can build their own word identification simultaneously fluency, vocabulary and comprehension skills[15].Therefore, to improve students reading comprehension skills, pre-reading activities before reading class are necessary.

Table 8

Test of Difference between the Posttest Scores of the Two Experimental Groups of Respondents after using the Pre-reading Activities

Reading Comprehension	Experimental Group 1		Experimental Group 2		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Verbal Interpretation
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD				
	Identifying main <u>idea</u> and key details	5.90	1.77	5.60				
Sequencing	8.13	2.40	8.47	1.78	-0.611	58	0.544	Not Significant
Direct recalling questions	9.23	0.90	8.40	1.83	2.239	58	0.029	Significant
Making inferences or predictions	5.43	1.87	4.90	1.97	1.075	58	0.287	Not Significant
Identifying unfamiliar vocabulary	4.03	1.43	4.63	2.89	-1.018	58	0.313	Not Significant
Total	6.54	1.75	6.4	2.00				

Legend: Sig (2-tailed) \leq .05 (Significant); Sig (2-tailed) \geq .05 (Not significant)

Table 8 shows the results of the mean posttest scores of the two experimental groups when compared. It can be seen from the table that out of 5 comprehension skills, only direct recalling questions were found to be with significant difference with t-value of 2.239 and p-value of 0.029 at .05 level of significance. This indicates that before and after the conduct of the study, significant difference with their scores in direct recalling questions have shown great improvement since direct recall questioning requires clarifying, understanding and remember the information. Compared to other skills, direct recalling questions focused on memorization of what was discussed in the passage or story. The answers can be found already from what they read. The experimental group 1 has higher mean scores compared to experimental group 2, that's why significant difference in the posttest is found. In terms of identifying main idea and key details, experimental group got a higher mean score than experimental group 2. In sequencing as well as in identifying unfamiliar vocabulary, experimental group 2 got a higher mean score than experimental group 1. In direct recalling questions as well as in making inferences or predictions, experimental group 1 got a higher mean score than experimental group 2. Even if there's a little improvement in the results, for the teacher, it is still an achievement. This implies that reading activities matter in the improvement of the comprehension skills of the students specially if they enjoy what they read and have the pleasure of understanding each passage or story [16]. Thus, exposing students to different reading activities is important.

Nonetheless, the rest of the skills such as identifying main idea, sequencing, making inferences or predictions and identifying unfamiliar vocabulary have no significant difference. This shows on the t-values of 0.776, -0.611, 1.075 and -1.018 with p-values of 0.441, 0.544, 0.287 and 0.313 respectively. These results of no significant difference imply that both experimental groups have

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the same level of comprehension skills after they have undergone the treatment or the experiment. They have both improved their reading comprehension skills only no one is higher than the other, since their scores are closely similar and belong to the same of performance level. It implies that both activities used in the conduct of the study are somehow effective in improving the reading comprehension skills of the students.

It's crucial for children to have good reading skills and understanding to do well in school [17]. These skills help them access different subjects and enhance their communication and language abilities. Additionally, providing students with activities to do before discussing the text in class significantly improves their reading performance.

Children who enjoy reading every day do better in reading tests compared to those who don't. They also learn more words, gain more knowledge about different things, and understand other cultures better.

Based on the results of the mean pretest and posttests of the two experimental groups, pre-reading activities have certainly improved their comprehension skills. This was supported by the literature mentioned based on the results and importance of the study.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The study focused in two sections of grade 9 and served as two groups who undergone the four pre-reading activities. Based on the results of the experiment, there is no significant difference in the mean pretest and posttest of the experimental group 1 using the KWL and graphics information pre-reading activities. However, there is significant difference in the direct recalling questions reading comprehension skill. In the same manner, there is no significant difference between the mean pretest and posttest of experimental group 2 using the WH questions and vocabulary based on the results of the test of difference. However, one similar variable to that of experimental group 1 has significant difference that is direct recalling questions reading competence. Also, there is no significant difference between the pretest scores of the two experimental groups of respondents before using the pre-reading activities. In terms of posttest of the two experimental groups, all the four variables have no significant difference although some improvement in the posttest scores is evident. But when compared, no significant difference was found among identifying main idea and key details, sequencing, making inferences or predictions, and identifying unfamiliar vocabulary. Nevertheless, only direct recalling questions were found to have significant difference in the mean posttest scores.

Based on the study's results and conclusions, several recommendations are hereby suggested. Since the results of the study found to have some improvement on the reading comprehension, teacher may continue using pre-reading activities that will engage the students to read more different types of reading materials. Also, future researchers may consider conducting studies related to this like using other pre-reading activities that may help and encourage students to improve their reading comprehension. Additionally, teachers may use other pre-reading activities aside from the ones used by the researcher, reading materials that suit to the interest of the students are also suggested. Lastly, teachers of other disciplines may also use the pre-reading activities by the researcher to help them understand what they read and master the skills needed in the subject because comprehension matters in any discipline of work.

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